

Freedom, Agency and the Hermeneutics of Technology
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This paper is motivated by two decades of work in technology firms, observing the wide gulf that exists between the normative appeals of technology ethicists and the daily decisions made by the builders of technology. At conferences on technology ethics one hears the normative claims that practitioners should do certain things – they should make algorithms transparent; they should nudge users toward more ethical ways of life through product design. When asked how to account for the fact that engineers do not do these things, even after learning that they should, the response is generally that this is a question for psychology, or for business ethics, or for some other field.

Motivated to answer this question, to account for decisions that engineers make day-to-day, I have found such decisions to be largely mischaracterized in ways that perpetuate the self-interpretation of technical workers as having little agency in their work. The message, sometimes explicit, of projects in technology ethics is that, whereas artifacts may not be morally neutral, those who build them *are* applying instrumental, calculative reasoning to build towards a design, and must be taught the ethical ramifications of their finished designs. The upshot of this framing of technical work is that technology is an applied science, which allows little room for agency, and that the builders of technical products have agency primarily in the decision *whether* to build something. Once that decision is made, however, the agency of the builder is narrowed significantly to the instrumental application of physical and mathematical sciences.

This paper argues that technical rationality is never inherently calculative but is always embedded in interpretive practices with various goods, such that technical decisions are more authentically understood as hermeneutic interpretations of practical predicaments. The critical role of technology ethics, it seems to me, is to unpack and account for the full ethical content of the decisions faced by the designer and engineer, rather than instrumentalize such decisions. Such an account would restore the sense of ethical agency that the notion of technology as applied science espoused by engineering educators conceals from engineers.

This paper is thus situated within the concern for subjectivity, and the freedom and agency of the subject, that originates in Rousseau and Kant and continues through Romantic and then hermeneutic thought, most recently found in Gadamer and Taylor. This is in contrast to postphenomenological approaches to technology ethics that seek to break from what is described as transcendental understandings of technology in favor of empirical research into the ways that artifacts condition our lives. It is argued here that what is critiqued as transcendental understandings of technology, primarily the later Heidegger, is actually part of this longer tradition of concern for the freedom of the subject against the heteronomous demands of empiricist and rationalist epistemologies.

This paper attempts to develop this account of technical decision-making as embedded in interpretive practices, with references to many technical practices, in particularly one of the most technical of activities, the development of statistical models within AI and other fields.